

Bringing together African and European partners to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers.

One Year of SkincAlr: Building the Foundations for AI-Powered Skin NTD Detection in Africa

"This first year has been a whirlwind of activities, discussions, challenges, and achievements. What started as an ambitious vision has gradually evolved into a coordinated effort involving researchers, healthcare professionals, technical experts, policymakers, and community stakeholders across Europe and Sub-Saharan Africa, all working towards a common goal: improving the early detection and management of skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs)."

In this editorial marking one year since the launch of SkincAlr, project coordinator Gustavo (UPM) reflects on the origins of SkincAlr, the challenges and lessons learned, and above all the achievements of the past 365 days. He also looks ahead to the next four years and the work that lies ahead, emphasising one of SkincAlr's most distinctive features: collaboration and teamwork.

[Read the full editorial](#)

SkincAlr in depth

The SkincAlr journey | Episode 0: before the first image

Join us in Senegal, where partners [Sherwood](#) and [Centre Hospitalier de l'Ordre de Malte de Dakar - CHOM](#) are collaborating with dermatologists to test the prototype of the SkincAlr app. Across four locations in the country, this

fieldwork gathers real-world insights to shape an AI-powered tool for the early detection of skin-related neglected tropical diseases.

The team also took part in the **celebration of World NTDs Day** in Khombole, where CHOM received a token of recognition for their work, and partners had the opportunity to meet with the Senegalese Minister of Health.

Watch the full video

Explain the objectives of the fieldwork that TeaCup Lab is currently carrying out.

Discovery trip to Kenya

[TeaCup Lab](#), the SkincAIr partner responsible for conducting UX research for the development of the SkincAIr AI-powered mobile app, **began its fieldwork by travelling to Kenya**. A couple of weeks before they left, we interviewed them to find out more.

Watch the full video

From fieldwork to design: what Kenya taught us about building SkincAir

Written by Teacup Lab

From Fieldwork to Design: What Kenya Taught us About Building SkincAir

TeaCup Lab has been working on the ground in Kenya, **working closely with frontline healthcare workers** to understand how neglected tropical skin conditions (NTDs) are diagnosed and managed in real-life settings. In this article **they share** with us **three key takeaways** from this phase of the project: What technical foundations does SkincAir need?, What challenges did they identify?, What comes next for SkincAir?

[Discover more](#)

You are about to embark on your second
Discovery Trip, come to Ethiopia.
Why is it important to conduct this type
of fieldwork in different countries?

Discovery trip to Ethiopia

[TeaCup Lab](#), the SkincAlr partner responsible for conducting UX research for the development of the SkincAlr AI-powered mobile app, is **continuing its fieldwork, this time in Ethiopia**. A couple of weeks before they left, we interviewed the team to gain a better understanding of the **need for geographical diversity** in fieldwork.

Watch the full video

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**From fieldwork to design:
Lessons Learned from
Discovery Research in
Ethiopia**

Written by Teacup Lab

From Fieldwork to Design: Lessons Learned from Discovery Research in Ethiopia

In April, the [TeaCup Lab](#) team travelled to Ethiopia to **continue the discovery research for SkincAir**. This fieldwork followed the first round conducted in Kenya and allowed them to explore how the realities of frontline health work compare across different clinical and institutional contexts.

[Discover more](#)

Milestones

SkincAlr

PRESS RELEASE

#2

published

The SkincAlr clinical validation study is now officially registered on ClinicalTrials.gov

SkincAlr press release #2 | The **clinical validation study**, 'Early Detection and AI-Based Management of Skin-Related Neglected Tropical Diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa by Frontline Health Workers (SkincAlr)', **has now officially been registered** with [ClinicalTrials.gov](https://clinicaltrials.gov), the international clinical trial registry hosted by the US [National Library of Medicine \(NLM\)](https://www.nlm.nih.gov).

**Read the SkincAlr
press release #2**

Events

SkincAir at the 'Living Borders' Symposium

The ['Living Borders'](#) symposium took place from 21 to 23 May at the Eikones Forum in Basel.

Gil Sharvit of the [Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts](#) represented SkincAir at the event.

[Discover more](#)

SkincAir stresses the importance of ethical tech governance

On 18 May, **Celia Fernández** from [UPM](#) represented SkincAir at the event, ['Open Government in Spain: Consolidation, Evaluation and Innovation in Open Governance'](#).

[Discover more](#)

SkincAir at the SEFI 7th SIG Ethics Spring Symposium

The [SEFI 7th SIG Ethics Spring Symposium 2026](#) was held from 20 to 24 April in Sofia, Bulgaria.

Celia Fernández from [UPM](#) gave a presentation on the **ethics of care within SkincAir**.

[Discover more](#)

SkincAir is one of the key topics at the 'Try IT!' Congress

From 16 to 20 March, the [UPM](#) hosted the ['Try IT!'](#) congress.

SkincAir was one of the main topics discussed during the roundtable discussion, 'From Reactive to Predictive Medicine'.

[Discover more](#)

SkincAir Project

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